
EXTENT OF POLYTECHNIC-INDUSTRY COLLABORATION IN SKILLS ACQUISITION OF OFFICE TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT PROGRAMME IN DELTA STATE

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Abstract

The study determines the extent of polytechnics-industry collaboration in skills acquisition of office technology and management programme in Delta State. It adopts the descriptive survey design. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study was 848 which include 24 lecturers and 824 students. A sample size of five hundred and twenty six (526) was drawn from the students' population while all the lecturers were involved in the study. This brought the respondents to 540 respondents. A structured questionnaire, design with 84 items questions in three parts was validated by experts in Office Technology and Management department. The reliability of the instrument was established through the use of Chronbach Alpha Statistics which yielded overall reliability coefficient of 0.87. The data collected from respondents were analyzed using descriptive mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study concluded that polytechnics collaborate with some local industries to a high extent but collaborate with foreign industries/universities to a low extent. It was recommended among others that polytechnics should strengthen existing policies that enable them collaborate with industries in order to foster practical learning to enable students acquire better and enhance skills.

Keywords: Polytechnic, Collaboration, Skills, Acquisition, Office Technology and Management, Entrepreneur

Introduction

Polytechnic education in Nigeria is among the tertiary education institutions responsible for training middle level manpower. It is a vital component of Nigeria's education system that provides technical and vocational training for thousands of students. The polytechnic education according to Ikelegbe (2020) is saddled with the promotion of technical and vocational education and training, technology transfer and skills development to enhance the social-economic development of Nigeria. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) through the National Policy on Education positioned that, part of the goal for which tertiary education is established includes; to contribute to national development through manpower training and to provide accessible and different quality learning opportunities in formal and informal education in response to the needs and interest of all Nigerians. This is exactly what the polytechnic system is thriving to achieve through training of eligible students and through research in order to meet industries needs and global standards.

According to Umar, Ishiyaku and Ishaku (nd), the National Policy of Education (NPE) document specified how higher education goals shall be pursued in Nigeria. These includes teaching, research and development, virile staff development, generation and dissemination of knowledge, and variety of modes of programmes including full-time, part time, block release, day release, sandwich etc. These set goals are to be achieved through teaching, research, staff development programs, access to training funds such as Tertiary Education Trust Fund (Tetfund), Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES), maintenance of minimum education standard through agencies and inter-institutional cooperation, among others.

Dung-Gwom (2014) offered some useful definition of polytechnic education as, career focused applied education that spans trades through advanced degrees, delivered in an environment where students receive hands-on training that enables them to more readily apply their skills. The emphasis on hands-on training clearly points to technical and vocational training which is offered by the polytechnic education.

In Nigeria, polytechnic education is recognized as part of tertiary institutions whose aim is to provide middle level manpower to man the various sectors of Nigeria economy. The programmes offered by the polytechnics are designed as two tier programmes of studies, namely; the National Diploma (ND) and the Higher National Diploma (HND) with one year period of industrial experience which is a pre-requisite for entry into the Higher National Diploma programme (Ikelegbe, 2020).

The polytechnic programme is supervised by the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE). The board is saddled with regulating and overseeing education programme, offered by technical institutions including polytechnics, monotronics through an accreditation process with the aim of providing standardized minimum guide curricula for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in Nigeria (NBTE, 2015).

In the views of Otunta in Onomiwoi (2020), the polytechnic education provides; Students with "life skills" to become productive entrepreneurs, empower graduates with technical skills needed to enhance productivity and national development, enable students to learn the art of vocational and technical education in the most efficient and economical manner possible, teaches skills of sound citizenship in the art of vocational and technical education and instilling the virtue of dignity of labour and human resource development for national development by disseminating knowledge in various forms.

No doubt, benefits provided by polytechnic education in Nigeria are in-exclusive as researchers have agreed that if any nation must keep pace with technological demand of the world, such a nation must align itself with vocational and technical education offered by the polytechnics.

Entrepreneurship according to Nwosu and Okoro (2023) has been recognized as one of the necessary conditions for economic development and empowerment. In Nigeria, entrepreneurship training amongst other things, seeks to provide graduates with knowledge, skills and attitude required to work and earn a living. UNESCO (2008) stated that entrepreneurship education consists of all kinds of experiences that give the students ability and vision of how to access and transform opportunities of different kinds into profitable economic ends. This definition sees entrepreneurship training as a means of developing a business ability and vision in an individual. Ability and vision speaks of foresight, competencies/skills which enable a business to be successful. Entrepreneurial skills are simple business skills which individuals acquire to enable them function effectively in the business environment..

Office technology and management programme is a course of study in tertiary education in Nigeria such as universities, colleges of education and polytechnics. In the polytechnic, OTM as a programme of study is offered at the National Diploma (ND) and at the Higher National Diploma (HND) level. According to the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) (2009), the programme prepares students for effective work competencies, psychological and practical skills, knowledge of occupations in various economic sectors, and social life for effective work performance in employment and self-reliance. The courses provided in the NBTE OTM programme are very necessary in today's technological world. This is also the views of Adanma (2022) when he stated that, most of the courses in OTM curriculum programme place a strong emphasis on developing digital skills, that are crucial in today's technological driven workplaces.

The OTM programme goals according to Adanma (2022) are to teach contemporary secretarial skills. In addition, OTM graduates are expected to be employable, and also skilled with the ability to start small businesses like photocopying, computer and internet centers, laptop and phone repair centers, computer and phone accessory sales, provision stores operator, book binding centers, reprographic and printing press centers, rental services among others. To be able to be self-employed or to be employable, the OTM graduate must/should acquire the necessary skills needed to function. These experiences however cannot be acquired from the classroom alone without collaborating with existing companies or small scale businesses where the practical skills can be learnt before graduation.

Skill acquisition is the manifestation of ideas and knowledge through training geared towards instilling in the youths the spirit of entrepreneurship needed for meaningful development (Douli in Ariwodo & Emeasoba, 2023). Skills does not depend solely upon a person's fundamental innate capacities but must be developed through training practice and experience an individual acquired. Okoro and Ursuala (2012), noted that two fundamental issues are used when a skill is to be acquired, the first is the conditions which promote acquisition and the second is the change that will occur when skill is acquired, the change gives birth to a new knowledge and ability to perform, or to be self-employed or self-reliance.

The term institution/school-industry collaboration according to Akpojotor and Chukwuemeke (2024) is used to describe the relationship between tertiary institutions and related industries. The aim is to bridge the gap between classroom learning and industrial

practice. This relationship between tertiary institutions and industries is to lead to industrialization and technological development. The forms of relationship differ according to the extent of interconnections between the industries and institutions involved.

Internationally, government and industries stakeholders have actively pursued collaborative arrangement with schools, such arrangement operate through policy and funding mechanisms This is also done to address needs of postindustrial age, knowledge economy and provide a range of benefits for enhance innovation and improve social educational outcomes for learners and employees group (James, Hitendra and Flynn in Ikelegbe, 2020). In the views of Walters (2016), collaboration within schools and industries allows for efficient skill building in the students. Collaboration can help address supply of educational services to geographically dispersed-locations which solves some barriers and difficulties for rural and remote students and perhaps help the education sector to keep pace with knowledge innovation.

Evidence abound that in business context, partnership collaboration allow convergence of partners perspectives which can result in innovative education ideas, directly relevant to their workforce, hence co-produced educational programmes which create genuine and direct value for both the school (students as ultimate beneficiaries) and for industries (Walters, 2016). Also, Walters added that collaboration can provide access to resources that are beyond the financial capacity of schools. These resources include equipment's that are industry standard, which is in contrast to simple options available in school laboratories and workshops as well as personnel who are experts in their respective fields.

Again, collaboration can assist schools produce innovative contextualized industry based curriculum which can produce knowledge transfer and workplace readiness of potential employees as it is a platform for future recruitment of employees. So it is a win-win collaboration for both the institutions and the industries.

According to Abiola (2023), the industrial sector of every economy consists of tendency to work persistently with materials to produce goods. She added that today's industry is changing and new design methodologies and organizational models are emerging, as design shifts from focus on physical products or digital interface to more holistic experience. This means that to fit into an organization of today, the office technology and management graduate must be skillful in the desired area of the industry.

According to Mbah, Obi and Ehimen (2018), industry and institutions collaboration are strategies required for preparation for training of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) students, (OTM students inclusive) to complement classroom experience in order to acquaint them with skills for practical teaching and employment in industries after graduation. Institutions of learning and industries collaboration is therefore a partnership between formal education and industry sector to create enabling training environment for students to acquire on the job experiences, knowledge, skills and appropriate attitude to work. Rossi in Abiola (2023), stressed that industry collaboration with schools could be made to meaningfully contribute to the training of students in appropriate and contemporary skills that relate to their interest. This is particularly important in the development of capabilities needed for good occupational adjustment. Shetima (2020) stressed that granting industry visit to various schools for relevant exposure in practical work and granting business education/OTM students SIWES opportunity are a few among school industry collaboration required for employment in the industry upon graduation from school. It is therefore necessary to allow a

functional office technology and management programme to effectively partner with industries to acquire required skills that will enable graduates fit into the work place.

Statement of the Problem

Office technology and management programme is design to enable graduands to acquire vocational and technical skills that will enable them fit into the workplace or to be self-employed and also employ others. However, research has shown that graduates of OTM have been plagued by inability to get jobs in industries and they also lack confidence to start their own business. Most industries have often complained of inadequate skills required especially in the current cutting edge technology, and also low practical know-how, low self-esteem among graduates is a bane on the programme. This means there is a serious mismatch between the need of the industries and the skills acquired by graduates of OTM from the polytechnics.

The researcher therefore is worried on the quality of skills imparted into the students that do not meet the standard of skills demand in the industry, this shows there is gap that needs to be eliminated. With the present state of information available, it seems that the present students industrial work experience scheme (SIWES) programme that is designed to foster collaboration with industries has not measured up to expectation as it has experienced failure in so many areas of its operations, such as the supervision components, students unseriousness, lack of institutions interest in the SIWES programme and absence of required skills for students job placement. With the observed lapses, it becomes pertinent to determine the extent of polytechnic-industry collaboration in entrepreneurial skill acquisition among students of OTM programme in Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. To what extent have polytechnics and industries collaborated in developing effective entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students of Office Technology and Management programme?
2. To what extent have polytechnics and industries collaboration faced challenges that hinders effective entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students of Office Technology and Management programme?
3. What are the strategies required for polytechnics and industries to collaborate in developing entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students of Office Technology and Management programme in Delta State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study and were tested at 0.05 Alpha level of significance.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents, on the extent polytechnics and industries collaborate in developing effective entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students of OTM programme.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent polytechnics and industries collaboration faced challenges that hinder effective entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students of OTM programme.

Ho3: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students, on the strategies required for effective polytechnics and industries collaboration to develop entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students of OTM programme.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The area of the study is Delta state, while the population of the study comprised of 848, which is made up of 524 students and 24 lecturers. The simple random sampling technique was used to draw a sample of five hundred and twenty six (526) students while all the lecturers participated in the study, this bring the total number of respondents to five hundred and forty (540). Respondents were requested to rate the items on a 4 point rating scale of very high extent (VHE) 3.5-4.00, high extent (HE) 2.50-3.49, low extent (LE) 1.50-2.49, very low extent (VLE) 0.50-1.49 respectively. The instrument which is a structured questionnaire was validated by three experts in the field of Office Technology and Management. Chronbach Alpha Statistical Procedure (SPSS) was used to establish the reliability of the instrument. The reliability coefficients value of 0.82, 0.88 and 0.93 for cluster A1, A2 and A3 were obtained with an overall coefficient value of 0.87 in the 84 items questionnaire used for the study. Out of the five hundred and forty (540) copies of questionnaire administered on the respondents by the research assistants, five hundred and seventeen (517) copies were retrieved and used for the data analysis. This constitute 96% return ratio. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation at 0.05 level of significance. The application of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 23 was used for data analysis. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule for hypotheses was that any hypotheses which t-calculated value is less than the t-critical value of 1.96 is considered accepted. Whereas if it is more than the critical value is considered rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent have polytechnics and industries collaborated in developing effective entrepreneurial skills acquisition in OTM programme in Delta State?

Research question one is grouped into A to E.

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the extent polytechnic and industries collaborated.

S/N	Collaboration with:	Lecturers		Students		Total		Decision
		X	SD	X	SD	X	SD	
A.	Small enterprises such as;							
	1. Photocopying services	3.12	0.86	3.08	1.11	3.14	0.54	HE
	2. Typing and document preparation	3.22	0.96	3.26	0.94	3.24	0.85	HE
	3. Reprographic printing (large-format printing, scanning) etc.	3.38	0.52	3.29	0.52	3.30	0.52	VHE
	4. Digital printing services (ID Cards, banners etc.)	3.36	0.66	3.24	0.24	3.30	0.45	HE
	5. Document management Graphic design	3.39	0.46	3.32	0.51	3.36	0.52	HE
	6. Mobile services rendering	3.27	0.82	3.24	0.86	3.25	0.84	HE
	7. Book binding	2.75	1.12	2.80	1.16	2.79	1.14	HE
	Weighted Average Mean	3.29	0.77	3.20	0.75	2.91	0.69	HE
B.	Collaboration with small manufacturing such as;							
	8. Paint manufacturing (artistic, decorative and protective)	2.56	1.14	2.61	0.96	2.59	1.05	HE
	9. Chemical (primers, sealers, vanishers)	2.41	1.26	2.56	1.14	2.49	1.20	LE

	10. Coatings (architectural, industrial and automobiles)	2.36	1.28	2.47	1.18	2.41	1.23	LE
	11. Soap detergent manufacturing	2.35	1.38	2.46	1.19	2.40	1.29	LE
	12. Perfume/air freshner manufacturing	2.36	1.08	2.47	1.18	2.41	1.13	LE
	13. Disinfectant manufacturing	2.33	1.14	2.36	1.18	2.34	1.16	LE
	14. Fruit production	2.32	1.16	2.36	1.18	2.34	1.17	LE
	Weighted Average Mean	2.04	1.19	2.18	1.20	2.08	1.19	LE
C.	Collaboration with foreign and local universities such as;							
	15. Exchange programmes	2.01	1.36	2.24	1.20	2.12	1.28	LE
	16. Research and development	2.16	1.28	2.28	1.22	2.22	1.25	LE
	17. Use of facilities (laboratories and library)	2.16	1.24	2.18	1.20	2.17	1.22	LE
	18. Use of experts (teachers and technologist, technicians)	2.18	1.26	2.32	1.14	2.25	1.20	LE
	Weighted Average Mean	2.12	1.27	2.06	1.14	2.19	1.23	LE
D.	Collaboration with cottage industries such as;							
	19. Food and beverages (bread making, tea, wine etc.)	2.04	1.24	2.24	1.28	2.14	1.26	LE
	20. Textiles and apparel (tailoring, knitting, dress making, upholstery and furniture, leather goods, jewelry).	2.26	1.28	2.20	1.25	2.23	1.27	LE
	21. Craft and decore (pottery and ceramics, glassblowing)	2.16	1.26	2.21	1.28	2.18	1.27	LE
	22. Candle making and basket weaving	2.12	1.26	2.18	1.28	2.15	1.27	LE
	Weighted Average Mean	2.14	1.26	2.20	1.27	2.18	1.26	LE
E.	Collaboration with large firms such as;							
	23. Telecommunication firms (MTN, Globalcom etc.)	3.11	1.11	3.02	0.89	3.06	1.00	HE
	24. Banks (First bank, Zenith Bank, Access etc.)	3.36	0.66	3.34	0.66	3.35	0.65	HE
	25. Oil and gas (NNPC, SPDC, Chevron etc)	3.25	0.92	3.04	0.72	3.14	0.82	HE
	26. Manufacturing (Dangote, Unilever, Nigeria Brewery, Nestle etc.)	3.20	0.96	3.00	0.58	3.10	0.77	HE
	27. Construction firms (Julius Berger Nig., RCC Nigeria, Setroco Nigeria etc.)	3.01	0.62	2.68	1.12	2.84	0.87	HE
	28. Food and beverages (coca-cola, flour mills, seven up Nig. Etc.)	3.16	0.54	3.28	0.72	3.22	0.63	HE
	29. Insurance (AILCO insurance, Leadway Insurance, Zenith insurance etc.)	3.04	0.60	3.20	0.86	3.12	0.73	HE
	30. Retail shops (shoprite, spar Nig, Jumia Nig, Konga etc.)	3.16	0.54	3.48	0.50	3.32	0.52	HE
	31. Aviation (Airpeace, Arik air, Azman Air etc.)	2.20	1.26	3.24	0.58	2.72	0.92	HE
	32. Power and energy (PHCN, NERC, Egbin Power etc)	3.16	0.54	3.26	0.72	3.21	0.64	HE
	33. Media (NTA, FRCN, Punch etc)	3.14	0.52	3.11	1.11	3.12	0.81	HE
	34. Technology (interswitch Nig., Systems specs, Zinox Technologies etc.)	3.30	0.62	3.34	0.66	3.35	0.61	HE
	Weighted score	2.84	0.74	3.16	0.76	3.13	0.74	HE

Table 1 above showed response of lecturers and students in Delta State Polytechnics, Ogwashi-Uku and Otefe-Oghara on the extent of polytechnics and industries collaboration in

developing effective entrepreneurial skills acquisition in office technology and management. The responses indicated that collaboration with small enterprises in serial No. A, 1-7 has weighted average mean of 2.91, which is rated high extent, the low range of the standard deviation of 0.69 showed that respondents were not very far in their responses. This shows that small enterprise and the polytechnics in Delta State collaborate to a high extent.

Research question 1B, 1C, 1D, on collaboration with small manufacturing, collaboration with foreign and local universities, collaboration with cottage industries and collaboration with large firms were weighted average mean of 2.09, 2.12 and 2.14 which is rated low extent with standard deviation of 1.19, 1.19 and 1.26.

However, research question 1E which is on collaboration with large firms has a weighted average mean of 3.34 which is high extent with a standard deviation of 0.62. The low range of the standard deviation of 0.62 indicates the respondents have similar opinions.

Research Question 2: To what extent have polytechnics and industries collaboration faced challenges that hinders effective entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students of Office Technology and Management programme in Delta State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of the extent polytechnics and industries collaboration faced challenges

S/N	Collaboration faces challenges such as:	Lecturers		Students		Total		Decision
		X	SD	X	SD	X	SD	
1.	Bureaucratic processes and red tape	3.85	0.36	3.92	0.40	3.88	0.37	VHE
2.	Lack of clear policies and guidelines	3.88	0.33	3.72	0.46	3.82	0.39	VHE
3.	Differences in values, objective, and mission of schools	3.71	0.45	3.56	0.58	3.66	0.51	VHE
4.	Absence of trust among collaborators	3.67	0.52	3.64	0.57	3.65	0.53	VHE
5.	Lack of awareness about benefits of collaboration	3.73	0.45	3.80	0.41	3.75	0.43	VHE
6.	Fear of intellectual property theft	3.67	0.52	3.56	0.65	3.63	0.57	VHE
7.	Insufficient funding for research	3.65	0.60	3.56	0.58	3.62	0.59	VHE
8.	Focus on academic pursuit – rather than industry needs	3.58	0.61	3.76	0.44	3.64	0.56	VHE
9.	Limited understanding of academic research work	3.54	0.50	3.72	0.46	3.60	0.49	VHE
10.	Lack of trust and skepticism among collaborators	3.71	0.46	3.64	0.57	3.68	0.50	VHE
11.	Lack of interest and motivation in schools which also affect students interest	3.69	0.47	3.56	0.65	3.54	0.54	VHE
12.	Differences in management culture of schools and industries especially in financial management	3.67	0.52	3.60	0.58	3.64	0.54	VHE
13.	Institutional learning culture not adapted to the need of industries collaboration	3.48	0.62	3.28	0.74	3.41	0.66	VHE
14.	Different expectations and goals	3.65	0.48	3.52	0.59	3.60	0.52	VHE
15.	Communication breakdown among institutions and industries	3.73	0.45	3.80	0.41	3.75	0.43	VHE
16.	Insufficient resources for research and development	3.67	0.52	3.56	0.65	3.63	0.57	VHE
17.	Limited understanding of academic research process	3.65	0.60	3.56	0.58	3.62	0.59	VHE
18.	Limited understanding of industry needs	3.58	0.61	3.76	0.44	3.64	0.56	VHE

19.	Fear of failure and risk aversion	3.54	0.50	3.72	0.46	3.60	0.49	VHE
20.	Limited expertise and knowledge	3.71	0.46	3.64	0.57	3.68	0.50	VHE
21.	Absence of feedback	3.69	0.47	3.50	0.65	3.54	0.54	VHE
22.	Geographic distance and logistics	3.67	0.52	3.60	0.58	3.64	0.54	VHE
23.	Limited access to technology and equipment	3.48	0.62	3.28	0.74	3.41	0.66	VHE
24.	Insufficient time and resources	3.65	0.48	3.52	0.59	3.60	0.52	VHE
25.	Limited evaluation and monitoring mechanisms	3.71	0.46	3.64	0.57	3.68	0.50	VHE
	Weighted Average Mean	3.67	0.46	3.35	0.57	3.63	0.52	VHE

From the result of the study in research question 2, Table 2, all the respondents i.e. lecturers and students weighted average mean is 3.63, while the standard deviation is 0.52. This indicated that respondents rated all the constructs on the extent polytechnic and industries collaboration faced challenges that hinder effective entrepreneurial skills acquisition among student of Office Technology and Management Programme as very high extent. With the low standard deviation of 0.52, this shows that respondents opinion do not differ remarkably on the items presented for the research study.

Research Question 3: What are the strategies required for effective polytechnics and industries to collaborate in developing entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students of Office Technology and Management programme in Delta State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of the strategies required for polytechnic and industries for effective collaboration.

S/N	Strategies for effective collaboration	Lecturers		Students		Total		Decision
		X	SD	X	SD	X	SD	
1.	Polytechnics/OTM programme should partner in innovative activities to develop areas of common interest.	3.48	0.64	3.65	0.56	3.57	0.60	VHE
2.	Polytechnics and industries should regularly host industry-academia conference	3.28	0.60	3.20	0.72	3.26	0.66	VHE
3.	Polytechnics and industries should develop training and capacity building programs	3.76	0.46	3.40	0.77	3.58	0.61	VHE
4.	Polytechnics and industries should engage in knowledge sharing initiative	3.83	0.44	2.95	0.80	3.39	0.62	HE
5.	Polytechnics and industries should develop clear goals and objectives	2.80	1.01	3.72	0.46	3.26	0.73	HE
6.	Polytechnics and OTM programme should advocate to increased government funding	3.11	0.74	3.56	0.58	3.33	0.66	HE
7.	Public private partnerships should be encouraged.	3.35	1.02	3.64	0.57	3.50	0.76	VHE
8.	Clear communication channels should be encouraged.	3.55	0.64	3.80	0.41	3.68	0.52	VHE
9.	Trust building initiative should be develop	3.84	0.32	3.72	0.46	3.78	0.39	VHE
10.	Polytechnics and industries should encourage formation of joint venture	3.85	0.33	3.52	0.54	3.69	0.43	VHE
11.	Polytechnics should invite experts from industries as resource persons to demonstrate skills and production techniques to stimulate students learning	3.71	0.46	3.56	0.58	3.60	0.50	VHE
12.	Deliberate policies should be put in place for students to be absorbed by industries for SIWES	3.67	0.52	3.80	0.41	3.73	0.50	VHE

13.	Agreement of jointly sharing of instructional training facilities between polytechnics and industries	3.73	0.45	3.76	0.44	3.74	0.44	VHE
14.	Proper monitoring/supervision of ND OTM students on SIWES	3.67	0.52	3.72	0.48	3.70	0.50	VHE
15.	Increase in polytechnics/OTM programme students awareness on the benefits of collaboration	3.65	0.60	3.64	0.57	3.64	0.59	VHE
16.	National Board for Technical Education NBTE should allow polytechnics to enrich their local content in order to meet up the technological age.	3.70	0.72	3.56	0.65	3.63	0.64	VHE
17.	There should be the need for effective use of talents and synergy among collaborative polytechnics and industries in the area of entrepreneurship programme	3.75	0.88	3.64	0.57	3.40	0.72	HE
18.	Proper orientation should be held for OTM program students before proceeding on SIWES.	3.88	0.30	3.56	0.65	3.72	0.48	VHE
19.	Polytechnic and OTM programme students should be encourage by allowing them to visit industries on excursion	3.50	0.67	3.60	0.58	3.55	0.62	VHE
20.	Polytechnics/OTM programme should organize learning experience for students based on industry needs.	3.40	0.68	3.72	0.46	3.56	0.57	VHE
21.	Collaborative research grant should be develop	2.85	0.77	3.48	0.62	3.17	0.69	VHE
22.	Intellectual property policies should be created	2.80	0.75	3.28	0.74	3.04	0.74	VHE
23.	Resources and facilities should be shared	3.10	0.88	3.64	0.57	3.37	0.72	VHE
24.	Crowd funding campaigns should be used to raise fund to assist institutions and students.	3.87	0.32	3.72	0.46	3.80	0.39	VHE
25.	Clear guidelines should be put in place in establishing memorandum of understanding (MOUs) for lasting relationship among the polytechnics and industries.	3.90	0.40	3.76	0.44	3.83	0.42	VHE
Weighted Average Mean		3.54	0.57	3.87	0.56	3.42	0.58	HE

The result of the study in research question 3, table 3 shows lecturers and students responses on strategies required for polytechnics and industries for effectively collaborate in developing entrepreneurial skills acquisition in OTM program. The mean scores ranges from 3.04 – 3.83. This means that all the answers listed were answered in affirmative. The weighted average mean of 3.42, indicates that respondents rated all the items listed as strategies required for collaboration to a high extent. Also, with a low standard deviation of 0.42, this indicates that both lecturers and students are not distance away from their ratings.

Result of Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses formulated for the study were tested using t-test analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents on the extent polytechnics and industries collaborate in developing effective entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students of OTM programme.

Table 4: Summary of t-test on male and female respondents on extent of polytechnic and industries collaboration in developing effective skills acquisition

Variable	N	X	SD	Df	@	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male	127	3.31	0.42	513	0.05	0.448	1.96	NS
Female	390	3.35	0.48					

The data in Table 4 indicates that the t-calculated is 0.448 and the t-critical value is 1.960, at 0.05 level of significance and 513 degree of freedom, since the t-calculated is less than the t-critical. This means that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female respondents on the extent of polytechnics and industries collaboration in developing effective skills acquisition in OTM programme in Delta State. The null hypothesis is therefore accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent polytechnics and industries collaboration faced challenges that hinder effective entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students of OTM programme in Delta State.

Table 5: Summary of t-test on lecturers and students on the extent polytechnics and industries faced challenges that hinder effective entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students in OTM programme.

Variable	N	X	SD	Df	@	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Lecturer	24	3.07	0.38	513	0.05	1.862	1.96	NS
Students	493	3.40	0.36					

The result in Table 5, indicates that t-calculated is 1.862 and the t-critical is 1.960, at 0.05 level of significance and 513 degree of freedom. Since the calculated table value is less than the t-critical, this means that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of lecturers and students on the extent polytechnics and industries collaboration faced challenges that hinder effective entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students of OTM programme. The null hypothesis is therefore accepted.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students on the strategies required for effective polytechnics and industries collaboration to develop entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students of OTM programme.

Table 6: Summary of t-test on Lecturers and Students on the strategies required for polytechnics and industries collaboration to develop entrepreneurial skills in OTM programme.

Variable	N	X	SD	Df	@	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Lecturers	24	3.07	0.38	513	0.05	1.318	1.96	NS
Students	493	3.46	0.34					

The result of t-test in Table 6 shows that t-calculated is 1.318 and the t-critical is 1.96, at 0.05 level of significance and 513 degree of freedom. Since the t-calculated is less than the t-critical, this means that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of lecturers and students on the strategies required for polytechnics and industries collaboration to develop entrepreneurial skill acquisition in OTM programme. The null hypothesis is therefore retained.

Discussion of Findings

The findings in research question one revealed that small enterprises such as photocopying services, typing and document preparation, reprographic printing, digital printing services, document management and graphic design, mobile services rendering and book binding services collaborate with Office technology and management in polytechnics. The findings also shows that collaboration between polytechnics and small manufacturing such as paint manufacturing, chemical, coatings, soap detergent manufacturing, perfume/air freshner, disinfectant and fruit production was rated low. Also collaboration among foreign and local universities on exchange programmes, research and development, use of facilities, use of experts and collaboration with cottage industries such as food and beverages, textiles and apparel (tailoring, knitting dress making, upholstery and furniture), also craft and decoration and candle making and basket weaving was also rated low by respondents, Result regarding collaboration with large firms such as telecommunication firms, banks, oil and gas, manufacturing, construction firms, and insurance, was rated high in the opinion of respondents. The result in hypothesis one shows that there is no significant difference in the mean responses between male and female respondents, on the extent of polytechnics and industries collaboration. This finding is in line with the study of Onomiwoi (2016) whose findings revealed that OTM departments collaborate through SIWES programme with some industries. The study is also in line with Binuomote (2015) who reported that for OTM programme to acquire desirable skills. There should be adequate collaboration with industries in multiple areas to acquire skills for today and future jobs.

The findings in research question two revealed that polytechnics and industries collaboration faced challenges that hinder effective entrepreneurial skills acquisition among students of OTM programme. The findings on hypothesis two show that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers and students, therefore the hypotheses was retained. The findings corroborate with the study of Okolocha, Udegbunam and Ukwunoma (2024), that revealed that challenges faced by institutions in improving institution-industry collaboration varies from lack of trust, mismanagement, gap in communication and over dependence in foreign innovation and technologies. The findings also support the findings of Ikelegbe (2020) that there are myriad of challenges which has hinders adequate collaboration in order to improve skills among business education students in Delta State.

The result of the study in Table 3 indicates that all the items presented regarding strategies required for polytechnics and industries collaboration such as Office Technology and management should partner in innovative activities, regularly host industry academia conference, encourage formation of joint venture, have clear guidelines and have trust building activities etc. were rated high extent. The findings in hypothesis three show that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of Lecturers and students on the strategies required for effective polytechnics and industries collaboration to develop entrepreneurial skills acquisition among Office Technology and Management programme. The present study and the study of Akpojotor and Chukwuemeke (2024) are in agreement on the area of strategies such as sharing initiative, hosting industry and academia conference, partnering in innovative activities to develop areas of common interest. The study is also in consonance with Emeasoba, and Victor (2024) which stated that industries and institutions collaboration could strategically provide equipment that could assist in training students.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that polytechnics in Delta State, collaborate to a high extent with some industries, while they also collaborate to a low extent with others. Polytechnics also face some challenges that hinder the acquisition of skills in OTM program. Strategies such as partnering with industries in innovation activities to develop areas of common interest are necessary.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made:

1. Polytechnics in Delta State should strengthen the existing policies that enable them to collaborate with industries in order to foster practical learning that will enable for acquisition of more skills desirable for entrepreneurship especially in the ICT era, This could be achieved by involving all stakeholders in polytechnics such as NBTE, government sector, parents and industries.
2. The identified challenges could be minimized if bureaucratic process can be reduced, this will give clear guidelines and equally bring about trust among collaborators who will want to collaborate with the polytechnics.
3. There is need for polytechnics to re-design their work schedule especially in SIWES unit to include a broad team that will partner in innovative activities to develop areas of common interest within the institutions and industries. The SIWES unit should be empowered to negotiate with industries, on favourable terms that will arouse school, students and industries interest in continuous collaboration. This could be achieved through clear guidelines that will assist the institutions and industries before signing memorandum of understanding (MoU).

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